

THE COFFEE GROUNDS: INSIGHTS BY COFFEE SHOPS

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ABSTRACT: Coffee is one of the most valuable primary products in the world trade and its consumption causes the production of a lot of waste. The coffee grounds remain today a major focus to study, particularly for bioenergy purposes. Since it is possible to use coffee waste in many ways at level demand, it is also important to investigate the coffee waste at the supply level and provide important information for the development a proper supply chain. Conceivably, coffee shops' owners are the producer of such waste, their mean profile is still unknown. Therefore, in the circular economy framework, the study aims to analyze the coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds use relying on a sample of Italian coffee shops and to profile an average Italian coffee shop. Data were collected by using a web-based survey administered during the period October – November 2019 in Rome and the sample was 95 coffee shops. The descriptive statistics was applied. The findings shows that 57% of the sample did not know the circular economy concept and 62% of the respondents would be available to attend formation courses about this new concept. The findings showed also a mean profile of an Italian coffee shop: it has been running for 10 years, serving 347 cups of coffee per day and producing about 2 kg per day of coffee grounds. It is interesting to underline that, on average, the coffee shop owner was willing both to sell the coffee grounds for energy purposes and to buy services or products which use the coffee grounds (as energy comes from coffee grounds use). These findings point out that people are becoming more sensitive towards coffee grounds use, considering it as a suitable alternative feedstock for energy purposes. Even if this study relies on explorative approach, the findings allowed to draw an identikit of hypothetical coffee shop that could supply the coffee grounds to industries for energy purposes. Moreover, it provides further insights in the coffee shops' owners attitude towards coffee grounds use.

Keywords: coffee waste product, coffee waste utilization, coffee grounds, Italy

1 INTRODUCTION

Coffee is one of the most valuable primary products in the world trade (Blinová et al., 2017) and according to the International Coffee Organization (2020) its global production in 2019/20 is estimated at about 169.34 million bags; however, in 2020 world coffee consumption is expected to decrease by 0.5% to 167.81 million bags as the covid-19 pandemic continues to put pressure on the global economy and greatly limits out-of-home coffee consumption (ICO, 2020).

In general, coffee production cause many wastes (as coffee grounds) that could be used for many purposes, as production of fuel pellets (Picchio et al., 2020), substrate for biogas, bioethanol or biodiesel production, composting material for agricultural purposes, substrate for mushroom production, etc. (Blinová et al., 2017). The waste reuse is gaining more and more importance due to both the waste environmental impact (Du et al., 2018) and the growth world population that will reach 9.7 billion individuals in 2050 (United Nations, 2019). Moreover, the growth world population increase the rivalry among food crops and energies crops and reusing agricultural and industry residues is gaining interest throughout Europe (Stefanoni et al., 2020, Suardi et al., 2020, Latterini et al., 2020). In fact, if on one hand, researchers studied alternative food to feed the world population and to reduce the land use (see e.g. Palmieri et al., 2019; Palmieri et al; 2020a); on the other hand, some studies focused on agricultural residues use to reduce

land use for energy scope (Palmieri et al., 2020b; Palmieri et al., 2020c; Palmieri et al., 2020d). In this framework, the waste use could reduce both the environmental impact and the land use (Palmieri et al., 2020b). However, the reuse of coffee grounds remains today a major focus to study (Caramão et al., 2018) and many ways for its utilization is proposed in the international literature, including its direct use for biogas and electricity production (Economou et al., 2018), soil amendment (Santos et al., 2017; Jin et al., 2018), green composites (García-García et al., 2015), to improve wastewater treatment (Vítezová et al., 2019) and biodiesel production (Son et al., 2018; Kookos, 2018).

Being the circular economy defined as "an economic system that replaces the end-of-life concept with reducing, reusing, recycling, and recovering materials in production, distribution, and consumption processes" (Kichherr et al., 2017) and with the aim to create new business models and new responsible consumers (Kichherr et al., 2017), it could be interesting to focus on the attitude of coffee users towards coffee waste use. In other words, as it is possible to use coffee waste in many ways (as production of fuel pellets, substrate for biogas, bioethanol or biodiesel production, etc) at "level demand", it could be also interesting to study "the coffee waste supply chain" (i.e. coffee shops) at "supply level". To the best of our knowledge, no other study has been conducted concerning coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds use in Italy. Thus, the current study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the coffee shops' attitude

towards coffee grounds use of a sample of Italian shops. In addition, an average Italian coffee shop was profiled. Even if this study has an explorative purpose, it is an interesting research strand that, if further investigated, it could offer the opportunity to add important new insights on the matter. Besides, it can also fuel debates on a little-known issues as the topic of coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds use.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Data were collected by using a web-based survey administered during the period October – November 2019 in Rome. The survey was implemented *via* e-mail, and respondents recruited through invitations to participate in the online survey (Saphores et al., 2012). Moreover, snowball sampling recruitment was also adopted, using interpersonal relations to involve as many participants as possible (Palmieri and Perito, 2020).

The sample was 95 coffee shops and was not representative of the Italian coffee shops population. Moreover, the questionnaire was composed by questions that the current literature considers important to investigate the pro-environmental behaviors of people (Saphores et al., 2012). After analyzing the selected survey answers, the descriptive statistics was applied (Saphores et al., 2012) to profile the average coffee shop and its attitudes towards coffee grounds use.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results were calculated using R version 3.6.2 (Team, 2019) and showed that within the sample of 95 coffee shops, 14% of them have been working for 3 years, whilst 57% of the sample did not know the circular economy concept and 62% was available to attend formation courses about this new concept. Moreover, 66% of the respondents neither made an environmental budget nor of water consumption, energy consumption etc; 62% of the sample did know that coffee grounds could be used for many purposes and 68% believed that coffee grounds could be suitable for agricultural uses.

In the table I let us examine the mean profile of coffee shop studied.

Table I: The mean profile of coffee shop (N=95)

Variables	Mean (SD)
years	10.71 (11.30)
kg per day	1.9 (0.4)
circular economy (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.40 (0.60)
formation (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.61 (0.40)
general_consumes (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.34 (0.66)
coffe_reuse (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.77 (0.23)
coffe_reuse_how (No=0; agricultural use=1; cosmetic use=2; energy use=2)	1.00 (0.68)
will_sell (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.83 (0.17)
will_buy_product_by coffee (Yes=1 and No=0)	0.70 (0.30)

Source: our elaboration

Our findings showed also a mean profile of coffee shop. In fact, the coffee shop has been working for 10 years (*years*), it serves on average, 347 cups of coffee per day and produces about 2 kg per day of coffee grounds

(*kg per day*). The coffee shop owner was not aware of the circular economy concept. However, he was available to participate to formation courses about this new concept (training). The coffee shop neither made an environmental budget and or control its consumptions in terms of water consumption, energy etc, even if it knows that coffee grounds could be used for many purposes specially for agricultural use. It is noticeable to underline that, on average, the coffee shop owner is keen to both sell the coffee grounds for energy purposes and to buy services or products derived from the use of coffee grounds (i.e., as energy come from coffee grounds use or mushrooms cultivated with coffee grounds). Unfortunately, the literature still lacks specific studies on coffee grounds at supply level (i.e. coffee shops) that could have been helpful further argue our findings. In fact, these results are noteworthy because they highlight how people are becoming more sensitive to coffee grounds use, particularly if aware of the suitability as alternative feedstock for bioenergy production. Further studies are necessary to better understand the coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds use, in terms of their individual preferences, attitudes, or concerns.

4 CONCLUSION

Among the most common beverages appreciated by Italians, espresso is ranked quite high. However, making an espresso implies the production of waste, particularly the grounds that represents a burden for coffee shops' owners. The possibility to use it as feedstock for the production of pellets and biodiesel or as substrate for mushroom production would help to faint such a problem, but profile of the average Italian coffee shop is still not drawn. The study aimed to analyze the coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds relying on a sample of Italian coffee shops. The average Italian coffee shop has been working for 10 years, serving 347 espressos per day, and producing about 2 kg per day of coffee grounds. The coffee shop owner knows that coffee grounds is suitable for many purposes specially for agricultural use, and he is willing both to sell the coffee grounds for energy purposes and to buy services or products deriving from the use of coffee grounds (as energy come from coffee grounds use or mushrooms cultivated with coffee grounds). The study provides new insights on little-known issues concerning the coffee shops' attitude towards coffee grounds use, an important missing information that is fundamental for the proper development a given value chain.

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